

Effective Biometric Attendance System through Fingerprint among the Students

(Sistem Kehadiran Efektif Biometrik menggunakan Cap Jari dalam kalangan Pelajar)

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ABSTRACT

During the era now, attendance system come with various kind of method. Its importance for all student to ensure their attendance to the class. There are sort of problem facing by the school management especially on the side of teaching to control student's attendance. It brings mean to the student attitude for attending the class. Some of them taking a chance to not attend or skip the class. There also certain student has ability to make a fake attendance for themselves or another student. Now, the method of taking the student attendance to class are by write down the name, call out the student name and RFID attendance system. Some of the method lack in accuracy and come with some error. To overcome the issue and error, the attendance system be improved to the Biometric attendance system. Biometric attendance system that been made is by using the method of fingerprint. Biometric fingerprint attendance system classifies into two part which is hardware part and software part. Hardware part requires all the component such as fingerprint sensor, Arduino UNO, RTC module and others. For the software, it requires Arduino IDE and Coolterm software. The full development for this system may need some improvement in the future to overcome or reduce all the problem occur. During system development phase, some error was detected that may interrupt the results obtained. Therefore, the improvement for the system still require in order to bring a flying color results and minimize the error faced. Some part of the system and it improvement next day will make the attendance system more organized.

Keywords: Biometric; Attendance; Fingerprint; RFID; Arduino

ABSTRAK

Dalam era terkini, sistem kehadiran mempunyai banyak kaedah dan cara. Ia amat penting terhadap semua pelajar untuk memastikan kehadiran mereka ke kelas. Terdapat beberapa masalah yang terpaksa dihadapi oleh pihak pengurusan sekolah terutamanya bahagian pembelajaran dalam pengendalian kehadiran pelajar. Ini dikaitkan dengan sikap dan tingkah laku pelajar dalam menghadiri kelas. Segelintir pelajar mengambil kesempatan untuk tidak menghadiri atau ponteng daripada kelas tersebut. Ini juga boleh mengundang kepada mereka untuk melakukan kehadiran palsu. Pada kaedah sekarang, kaedah merekod kehadiran pelajar masih banyak dalam bentuk manual seperti menulis nama, pemanggilan nama dan juga sistem RFID yang juga telah dilaksanakan. Kaedah yang digunakan kurang dalam akurasi dan mempunyai keralatan. Untuk mengatasinya, sistem kehadiran biometric melalui kaedah cap jari telah dibangunkan. Ini kerana sedia maklum akan setiap individu mempunyai cap jari yang berbeza. Sistem ini terbahagi kepada dua perkakasan utama iaitu luaran dan dalaman. Sistem luaran merangkumi pengesan cap jari, mikro pengawal Arduino UNO, modul RTC penetapan masa dan lain-lain lagi. Bahagian perkakasan dalaman pula hanya melibatkan sistem Arduino IDE dan juga aplikasi Coolterm. Pada keseluruhan, sistem ini masih juga memerlukan penambahbaikan pada masa akan datang. Hal ini kerana, terdapat sedikit keralatan berlaku semasa pembangunan sistem dalam memperolehi hasil kajian. Oleh sebab itu, penambahbaikan pada sistem masih perlu untuk mendatangkan hasil kajian yang memuaskan dan mengatasi keralatan yang dihadapi. Sebahagian daripada sistem dan juga peningkatan dapat membantu sistem kehadiran agar lebih terkendali.

Kata Kunci: Biometrik; Kehadiran; RFID; Arduino

INTRODUCTION

Now, study and take a lesson very important to achieve own goal so that to gain the knowledge, people need to attend to the class. We can see that certain people which student are take this as their advantage to skip the class. Most important, they skip the class without their parent permission (Bhutada et al. 2019; Nazari et al. 2019).

To bring a solution to this problem, the biometric attendance system using fingerprint was proposed and develop. The whole system divided into three main part which are hardware, software and also interface part. Each part have its own function to run the system (Prince et al. 2016).

For the method to proceed this system, each part requires its own stuff. For example, Arduino UNO, fingerprint sensor R305, RTC Module, LCD display and other component need for hardware development. For the software and interface part, it only require Arduino UNO microcontroller to run the system by programming through Arduino IDE (Hendry et al. 2017).

Therefore, the most important thing is the method to develop the system. As we know, everything that been made not perfect so there are some error occur during the development such as data accuracy, system and component sensitivity also with unmatched component due to different version. As the system achieve its objective so the system can be success (Chawhan, 2013).

METHODOLOGY

In the development of the system, there are two main part of the system which are hardware part and software part. The method to take the attendance are through the enrollment and registration to the system. For the first part, the students need to enroll their fingerprint template before save in the system. It because the template is use for the next step in registration. The enrollment part is an importance step of methodology to make the system more complete. If there is some problem or error in the enrollment part so the registration part cannot be proceed (Krishnamurthi et al. 2015; Nordin et al. 2019).

In registration part, all record of fingerprint template use back to register. The template of fingerprint enrolls need to be justify and save in the system in order to make the attendance valid. Therefore, those two main parts of the attendance very importance to make the system become successful. Both part of the system can be done on the hardware part and software part. The proposed method helps a lot for the system development (Nawaz et al. 2009).

System Design and Procedure

To design and develop the system, there are few components need to build up the system such as fingerprint sensor R305, LCD display 16x2, RTC Module DS3231, Arduino UNO, Push Button, Buzzer and sort of circuit components such as breadboard, wire and others. The procedure proposed to the system classify into two which are enrollment and registration (Sourabh et al. 2019).

For enrollment, the student early need to enroll their fingerprint before register the attendance. In step of enroll the fingerprint, they need to put their fingerprint on the fingerprint sensor R305 to take the sample for the data template before save in the system memory which is EEPROM. After the fingerprint template stored so that the student can take their attendance successful (Patel et al. 2012).

The registration for the attendance as shown in Figure 1, they need to scan their fingerprint again on the sensor to ensure that it have match with fingerprint template saved during enrollment session. If there is match between registration and enrollment fingerprint template, the attendance can be record and valid to the system. Otherwise, the record for the system is non-valid (Moth et al. 2015).

FIGURE 1. Fingerprint Attendance System

System Equipment and Components

In Figure 2, it shown that the main component use to take and record the fingerprint. It have lot of feature and function in the system such 120 capacity fingerprint slot that can be store and can run in direct power of 3.6V to 6.0V.

FIGURE 2. Fingerprint Sensor R305

Arduino UNO shown in Figure 3 also take a big role to complete the whole system because it uses to be the interface in between hardware and software part. All the data also store in the Arduino UNO memory which is EEPROM especially the fingerprint data.

FIGURE 3. Arduino UNO

LCD display be functional to display and show the result or any justification on it screen same goes to Arduino IDE serial monitor. The screening uses in this system is 16x2 that mean 16 bits against 2 rows for the display as shown in Figure 4.

FIGURE 4. 16x2 LCD Display

In Figure 5, it show that the RTC module that uses in the system to set the time and date for attendace recorded. The type of module useds is RTC Module DS3231.

FIGURE 5. RTC Module DS3231

In order to accomplish the attendance system, RTC module or Real Time Clock module use to set up the date and time as prove for the student attend the class. The date and time

adjustment can be set by using Arduino IDE through program coding.

Flowchart of The System Process

Figure 6 shows the flowchart for the system process to take the attendance from begin to the last step.

FIGURE 6. Flowchart of the system

System Block Diagram

The proposed method for the whole system easier to see in form of diagram. As shown, the diagram representing the whole process of the system from the first step until the result display or obtained.

As shown in Figure 7, the block diagram represents the whole process of system. In classify into three main part which are hardware part, interfacing and software part. For the hardware, all the components involve require such as fingerprint sensor R305, RTC module DS3231 and circuit components. To interface the hardware to obtain the result, Arduino UNO microcontroller is uses as the interface to link all the main part of the system.

Through the Arduino IDE, the programmed coding upload to microcontroller to run the system. As the result obtained, LCD display 16x2 and buzzer are used. LCD 16x2 display the result on it screen while the buzzer functional when the fingerprint record and register valid and match to template stored during enrollment.

FIGURE 7. System Process

RESULTS

Fingerprint Enrollment

The enrollment is the first step of process in this system. The result of fingerprint enrollment and stored in the system memory which are in fingerprint sensor R305 and EEPROM shown in Figure 8 and 9. Fingerprint enrollment become basic to the attendance system of fingerprint to ensure repeatable fingerprint.

FIGURE 8. Fingerprint enrolment

FIGURE 9. Fingerprint stored

Based on the Figure shown in 6 and 7, enrollment process required some step before the fingerprint template stored in the memory. To enroll, the finger needs to scan for first time to take the fingerprint image and converted into form of template data. Then, the finger needs to put again on the sensor as the step to save and store the fingerprint.

Attendance Registration

Based on the Figure 10, we can see that the sensor has a capacity to store fingerprints. Figure show that the system detects the sensor and found the fingerprint that stored during enrolment process.

FIGURE 10. Fingerprint register with template

Figure 11 and 12 shown the result that display on the LCD display for registration fingerprint process. In Figure 11, student need to put their finger that already enrolled to scan for attendance record. If the fingerprint is valid as the template, buzzer will turn on shown that it already recorded. For Figure 12, LCD display shows that the attendance already recorded and save in the system data which is EEPROM. If the LCD display is not functional well, the result also can be check through

the software part which is Arduino IDE on the serial monitor.

FIGURE 11. Fingerprint Scanning Process

FIGURE 12. Attendance registered

Figure 13 represents result of attendance registered through serial monitor of Arduino IDE. Therefore, there are several ways that we can know the attendance already registered and save in the EEPROM.

FIGURE 13. Result display on Arduino Serial Monitor

To see more clear result and data, data that saved in the EEPROM extracted by using Coolterm Software. As we can see in Figure 14, there were 20 fingerprints stored in the system extracted using Coolterm software. It became prove to the school management to take the record of the student attendance.

FIGURE 14. Data extracted from EEPROM to Coolterm Software

DISCUSSION

A dynamic model of a rotary drum dryer has been developed. The model is shown to have good predictive capabilities. The model is used in a MPC. The MPC is compared with traditional feedback control in a simulation study based upon industrial plant data. The performance of the MPC is superior. In the case of unmeasured input disturbances, an AKF is used to estimate the disturbances. This approach gives a fairly good result (Didriksen 2002).

Advanced process control (APC) tools and technique sometimes were difficult to use and needed special hardware for implementation which cause raising in costs if this technology were applying on perhaps 20 to 30 years ago (Nordh 2015). Today's, with powerful computers, APC now is available everywhere and anytime at lower capital cost and with greater return on investment. For example, by apply MPC on certain unit operation needed specialist for developed accurate model of the process to reduce the probability of the failure in the plant. With this current technology, most of engineers can learned from the past history for developed more effective process. This critical review were focus on three process variable such as gas exhaust temperature in rotary dryer and product moisture. This process variable data can be source for manufacturer to run closer to desired target and push constraints with more confidence. Finally, more process variable can be control to get the desired product with low percentage of failure (Krishnan et al. 2017).

As the conclusion, in the future, the author hope that this system become more friendly in environment and advance (Dedy Irawan et al. 2018).

CONCLUSION

In this study has proof that attendance system is important to improve and minimize the problem such as skip or not attend the class and fake attendance. It also important to conclude the study without achieve the objectives of the system. For this study, there are two objective that been proposed to make this system. Firstly, to develop effective cost biometric attendance system by fingerprint. Next, to examine the effectiveness of the system developed. Some of the error and disadvantages already be solved such as time delay, LCD screen cursor and others by using coding in Arduino IDE (Sourabh et al. 2019).

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